

Stress-induced degradation and lifetime estimation in commercial power VDMOS transistors

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In this study commercial power VDMOS (Vertical Double Diffused MOS) transistors subjected to different stress conditions were investigated. Power VDMOS transistors are a type of power MOSFET designed for high-current and high-voltage applications. As shown in the technical documentation of the manufacturers, p-channel devices are usually designed to withstand currents of up to 6.8 A and drain-source voltages of -100 V. Similar situation is for the n-channel devices, they exhibit comparable characteristics, with maximum current ratings of about 5.6 A and drain-source voltages of $+100$ V. These transistors are realized in standard polycrystalline silicon gate technology with hexagonal unit cell structure and approximately 100 nm thick gate oxide. Despite most of modern MOS transistors are realized with very thin gate oxide, expansion of power devices in various industrial, automotive applications, nuclear power plants, medical equipment and similar, has led to increased interest for investigations of reliability of power VDMOS transistors. For example, in specific situations they can be used for switching power supplies, DC\DC converters, voltage regulator modules, motor drive applications and so on. In most of these applications devices could be exposed to different stress conditions and, as a result, a shift in the threshold voltage is observed. So the degradation phenomena in these devices under different stress conditions (irradiation, high electric field, hot carriers injection, unclamped inductive switching, negative bias temperature instability (NBTI), NBTI under magnetic field, NBTI and irradiation, self-heating and so on) has been the subject of extensive research.

A large number of researchers investigated the behavior of threshold voltage and analyzed the underlying changes of gate oxide-trapped charge and interface trap densities in power VDMOS devices subjected to different types of static and pulsed bias temperature stresses. Namely, this investigation is of great importance, bearing in mind that the electric fields and temperatures applied in NBT stressing can be approached to those achieved during the routine operation of power VDMOS devices in automotive and industrial applications. The responsible mechanisms that explain experimental data have not yet been fully explained. On the other hand, from the aspect of practical applications, it is necessary to know how the parameters of these devices change during the stress in order to be able to determine the lifetime. This is the main reason why several voltage and temperature lifetime models have been developed in the previous period.

In order to investigate device lifetime of commercial p- and n-channel power VDMOS devices IRF9520 and IRF510, respectively, devices were stressed up to 168 hours by applying negative or positive gate voltages in the range 30 – 55 V, with drain and source terminals grounded, at temperatures ranging from 125 to 175 °C. The threshold voltage was used as a degradation monitor, which is widely accepted as a well-suited parameter in the literature. The use of different voltage and temperature models for extrapolation to typical operation voltage and temperature, respectively, were demonstrated. A new approach in estimating the device lifetime for arbitrary operating conditions that assumes multiple extrapolation along both voltage and temperature axes was demonstrated. A detailed analysis was performed to compare both chosen model and selected failure criterion.

Keywords: VDMOS, degradation, NBTI, lifetime

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